

DG HOME and REA co-organised 2023 Projects to Policy Seminar

14 June 2023, 09:00 CEST - 15 June 2023, 17:00 CEST

EMERITUS POLICY BRIEFING

GENERAL SCENE SETTER: The European Commission (EC) is revising Directive 2008/99/EC¹, known as the Environmental Crime Directive, and it plans to create a new database where countries can report their prosecutions of environmental crimes. This initiative aims to obtain a clearer understanding of the magnitude of the problem. Additionally, the EC intends to standardise the definitions of crimes and to implement stricter sanctions.

Challenges faced by current policy: Nevertheless, the *application of sanctions today varies greatly* among Member States (MSs), with most countries considering them merely administrative issues, and their effectiveness in deterring offenders is questionable². The *lack of improvement in cross-border cooperation* since the Directive came into force is also a concern. Harmonising sanctions is crucial to *prevent forum shopping* by offenders who establish their businesses in countries where environmental crimes are less prosecuted. Environment Commissioner Virginijus Sinkevičius stressed the *importance of providing specialised training* to law enforcement officials, prosecutors, and judges and of ensuring that they have sufficient resources and tools to combat environmental crimes, although no specific funds are expected to be allocated for these efforts³. Additionally, in late December 2022, the Justice Ministers of the EU's MSs adopted their stance on the Environmental Crime Directive's revision, which aims to safeguard the environment through criminal law. However, the Ministers have diluted penalty and sanction levels and removed significant provisions from the original proposal by the EC. As a result, *MSs have not demonstrated a strong commitment to enhancing efforts* to combat environmental crimes.

THE EMERITUS PROJECT: the outcomes of the EMERITUS project are intended to address the challenges listed above by realising, in co-creation with a pull of actual end-users – i.e., law enforcement authorities (LEAs) and border guards (BGs) - a scalable-by-design digital platform to support environmental (waste-related) crimes' investigation thanks to the combined use of satellite data and images, drones, IoT sensors, and advanced data analysis algorithms, to be experimented in 4 highly relevant realistic use cases. This technological tool will be complemented

by an EMERITUS-designed investigation protocol, to guide LEAs/BGs in the use of digital technologies to investigate waste-related crimes, and a tailored training package combining both theoretical knowledge transfer and practical exercises. The combination of these results is intended to empower LEAs/BGs to actually use digital technologies in their operative activities, create specialised competences in the domain as well as peer-to-peer training ones, and, ultimately, improve the effectiveness of

¹ Directive 2008/99/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 November 2008 on the protection of the environment through criminal law, available at: [EUR-Lex - 32008L0099 - EN - EUR-Lex \(europa.eu\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/lexuri-uri.html?uri=CELEX:32008L0099-EN-20220818-EN-20220818)

² https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/policies/justice-and-fundamental-rights/criminal-justice/environmental-crime_en#revision-of-the-directive

³ <https://www.politico.eu/article/europe-sustainability-waste-eu-environmental-crime/>

environmental crimes investigation and prosecution. On top of these targeted activities, a Community of Practice (CoP) will be created to collect further inputs, engage a wider group of practitioners operating in this domain while fostering w cooperation attitude/practice, and develop policy-oriented and operative recommendations. At the European level, the results of the project could inform the development and revision of the Environmental crime directive, and the wider environmental regulatory framework, leveraging on both evidence from technical developments and co-creation activities with LEAs/BGs. Nationally, the project's findings could be used to enhance the capacity of LEAs/BGs to tackle environmental crimes and to align national laws with the EU's standards. At the local level, the project could provide valuable insights on how to operatively prevent and detect environmental crimes, thereby enhancing the implementation of environmental regulations and policies. Therefore, the project's results have the potential to contribute to a comprehensive and coordinated approach to combat environmental crimes across different levels of governance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The preliminary EMERITUS' interactions with the main actors involved in the fight against environmental crimes allowed collecting an initial set of recommendations that will continue to be elaborated and analysed through further iterations of consultations with the partners and the community of practice of the project. The table below presents these preliminary findings, and the potential benefits and disadvantages stemming from its implementation.

TOOLS

To create a **single platform** to guide the investigation operations for environmental crimes in the different MS to be easily used by the different states' LEAs/BGs.

- | | |
|--|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Improve the efficiency of investigations by streamlining processes, reducing duplication of effort, and promoting best practices. ✓ Improve data management by providing a centralised repository for environmental crimes-related data, making it easier to analyse and share data across different jurisdictions. | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ↓ Differences in law enforcement practices and procedures between different MSs could make it challenging to standardise the platform, which could reduce the effectiveness of data-driven decision-making. ↓ Creating a shared platform could encounter resistance from different MSs with different political or cultural priorities, levels of commitment to environmental protection, or law enforcement practices. |
|--|--|

Development of digital waste trafficking solutions.

- | | |
|--|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Efficient Monitoring ✓ Enhanced Compliance ✓ Cooperation at the EU level | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ↓ Integrating digital waste trafficking solutions into existing waste management systems may require compatibility with various databases, tracking mechanisms, and regulatory frameworks. |
|--|--|

CAPACITY BUILDING AND COOPERATION

To facilitate **cross-country interforce cooperation** among LEAs/BGs and other relevant operators through **continuous training, collaborative exercises, and regular communication.**

- | | |
|--|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Regular communication and collaboration provide opportunities for sharing intelligence, best practices, and lessons learned. This enables LEAs, BGs, and other operators to stay updated on emerging threats. ✓ By working together, different agencies and operators can pool their resources, expertise, and specialized skills. This synergy leads to increased operational efficiency, optimized resource allocation, and better utilization of personnel. ✓ It allows for a more comprehensive and holistic approach to law enforcement and border security. It enables agencies to address the entire spectrum of challenges, including organized crime, drug trafficking, human smuggling, and cybercrime, by leveraging the strengths and capabilities of different organizations. | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ↓ Different countries have their own legal frameworks, protocols, and jurisdictions. Coordinating across borders requires addressing these challenges, which can be time-consuming and complex. ↓ Communication and understanding can be hindered by language barriers and cultural differences. Differences in languages, customs, and operating procedures can lead to misunderstandings and misinterpretations, affecting effective cooperation. ↓ Unequal Capabilities, as LEAs, BGs, and other operators may have different levels of resources, training, and equipment. Disparities in capabilities could lead to challenges in coordination and interoperability, potentially impacting the effectiveness of joint operations. |
|--|--|

To integrate **dedicated specialised training programs** for the LEAs/BGs to **uptake new technological tools** (i.e., drones, sensors...) when investigating environmental crimes.

- | | |
|--|---|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Training programs provide officers with the knowledge and skills needed to use technological | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ↓ Acquiring, maintaining, and upgrading equipment can strain limited budgets. |
|--|---|

tools efficiently. This can lead to quicker and more accurate data collection, analysis, and interpretation, helping investigators identify and address environmental crimes more effectively.

- ✓ Expanded Surveillance and Monitoring: By incorporating new technological tools, LEAs and BGs can enhance their surveillance and monitoring capabilities in remote or inaccessible areas.

↓ Training programs necessitate allocating resources for instructors, facilities, and ongoing support, which may be challenging for some agencies.

↓ The sustainability of the programme depends on the availability of people capable of transfer those competences (→ e.g. *being exposed to train the trainers sessions*) Need to continue to specialize LEA/BGs forces to have resources actually capable of use technologies in the long run

DATA AND INTEROPERABILITY

To align waste classifications at the EU level and to create a standardised catalogue of harmful substances derived from landfills and their impacts.

- ✓ Facilitating the recognition of specific impacts as derivation from certain types of substances
- ✓ Facilitating/making possible to manage a common database of waste (legitimate/illegal) and facilitate interoperability of systems and exchange of info cross-border.
- ✓ Align and improve the way to define sanctions (to eventually reduce the exploitation of areas where sanctions are more limited)

↓ Time and effort intensity to align standards and foster the actual uptake at the national level

To improve the interoperability of environmental crimes-related data at local, national, and international levels through the harmonization of data collection.

- ✓ A more comprehensive understanding of the types and extent of environmental crimes, as well as the most affected areas.
- ✓ Access to consistent and integrated environmental crimes data can help law enforcement agencies to investigate and prosecute environmental crimes more effectively.
- ✓ Facilitate cross-border cooperation between countries, thus helping to combat transnational environmental crimes.

↓ Technical challenges.

↓ Legal and regulatory barriers that need to be addressed, including issues related to data privacy, data ownership, and data sharing across borders.

↓ Resistance to change among stakeholders can pose a significant barrier to harmonizing environmental crimes data collection and interoperability.

To create a centralised and integrated repository of national information with multidisciplinary data from different sources (satellite, aerial, terrain, documentary, legislative data, permits).

- ✓ Creation of differentiated accesses profiles
- ✓ Providing access for researchers/professionals to controlled samples of data for experimentation.
- ✓ Centralization of information about legal activities (that can help LEA/BGs to filter alerts/images)

↓ High need for cybersecurity protection of the platform/database

EMERITUS is an EU funded project realized by a consortium of 20+ partners from nine countries, bringing together a diverse range of expertise and knowledge. This project provides both protocols, training and technology to contribute in an effective way to the fight against the environmental crime to make a positive impact on the society by increasing the skills and resources at disposal of the authorities.

With a multidisciplinary approach, the consortium combines various fields of expertise, including expert trainers, geospatial analysts, software developers, consulting experts, and LEA's and BG's representatives, to develop innovative solutions.

For further information visit: <https://emeritusproject.eu/>

LinkedIn: [emeritus_EU](#)

Twitter: [@emeritus_EU](#)

Youtube: [emeritus_EU](#)